

PROSPECTING FOR ORE DEPOSITS USING GRAVITY SURVEY DATA

*Isgandarov E.**Associate professor,**Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku**Valiyeva D.**Master student,**Department of "Geophysics" Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University (ASOIU), Azerbaijan, Baku***Abstract**

This article is devoted to the exploration of ore deposits using gravity survey data. Gravity surveys are widely used in a wide range of mineral exploration applications. These include the search for geological structures favorable for oil and gas production, direct hydrocarbon exploration, the deep structure of the Earth's crust, and the search for solid and ore deposits. In Azerbaijan, gravity surveys were primarily used to explore for oil and gas deposits. However, recently, a focus has been shifted to ore deposit exploration, as Azerbaijan is located at the junction of the Greater and Lesser Caucasus mountain ranges, which provide favorable conditions for ore deposits. Several ore deposits are known to exist in the region, as well as deposits of precious metals (Dashkesan, Kelbajar, etc.). The article, using modeling methods, analyzes the possibilities of gravity exploration for searching for ore deposits (iron, copper and other metal deposits) that have excess density and are well displayed in the gravity field.

Keywords: gravity, gravity field, ore body, excess density, gravity gradients, local anomaly, modeling.

Introduction

Currently, gravimetric surveys are performed using high-precision digital instruments, providing accurate observed gravity field data, making it possible to solve a wide range of geological exploration problems, including prospecting for ore deposits. Prospecting for ore deposits is classified as direct mineral exploration, as ore deposits have a positive excess density. Ore deposits are represented by several types of ores. Most notable are massive sulfide ores, which have a density of 4.0–5.0 g/cm³, while the host rock density is 2.6–2.8 g/cm³. A distinct local maximum is observed above sulfide ore deposits. Iron ores include magnetite and hematite deposits, and gravity exploration is the primary method for prospecting for magnetite and hematite deposits due to their extremely high density. Often, the ore itself is too small to yield a gravimetric effect, but it is associated with large geological structures such as faults and contacts. Gravity surveys clearly reveal the boundaries of blocks of varying density, where hydrothermal solutions often concentrate. Ore deposits are also associated with intrusions of parent igneous bodies, which are associated with nickel, copper, or platinum deposits. These deposits are also associated with salt domes (gravity minima) and depressions at the periphery of which sulfur or polymetallic deposits may be present.

Gravity surveys are currently performed on land—high-precision ground surveys allow the delineation of even small vein bodies at shallow depths. Airborne gravity surveys are widely used to quickly cover large, hard-to-reach areas. In this case, the vertical gradient of gravity is primarily measured, as changes in gravity with altitude help better separate near-surface ore bodies from deep background structures. It should be noted that gravity exploration provides an ambiguous answer, as excess mass can be caused by either ore or simply by an outcrop of dense basement. Therefore, it is always used in conjunction with magnetic exploration (searching for magnetic minerals) and electrical exploration (searching for conductive ores). In modern conditions,

the geological industry is shifting to the search for complex and deep-seated ore bodies. In this context, gravity exploration remains one of the most cost-effective and informative geophysical methods. Due to the direct relationship between gravity and rock density, the method not only identifies structural traps but also directly detects excess masses, which are characteristic of most ore minerals (sulfide, ferrous, chromite, etc.) [9–10].

Despite the high resolution of modern gravimeters (e.g., Scintrex CG-6), the main challenge remains interpreting data in complex terrain and geologically heterogeneous host environments. Traditional methods of Bouguer anomaly analysis are often insufficient for distinguishing weak ore signals from strong regional background. The objective of this study is to identify and evaluate the feasibility of gravity exploration interpretation methods using simple and sophisticated orebody models that approximate real-world study objects. A significant number of publications have addressed the feasibility of using gravity and magnetic exploration for ore deposit exploration, as well as the results of this method's application in real-world areas [2,3,8].

Means and methods

The methodology for using gravity exploration to solve geological and geophysical problems mainly includes the following stages:

1. Reduction and introduction of corrections. Before analyzing the data, they are brought to a single common level - the geoid. For this, corrections are introduced for the height (free air), for the influence of relief and for the intermediate layer (Bouguer correction). The result is a Bouguer anomaly, which reflects only the heterogeneities in the earth's crust. It should be noted that foothill and mountainous regions are used for the search for ore deposits, and the exploration depth is much less than in oil gravity prospecting and is approximately several tens and hundreds of meters [7]. Introduction of corrections for free air, for the intermediate layer (Bouguer reduction) and for relief is an important factor when searching for local ore anomalies in rugged

terrain. The density of the intermediate layer should be taken as 2.67 g/cm³. Analysis of the density characteristics of rocks is important. The root mean square error of surveying for ore problems should typically be 0.01–0.05 mGal. To search for small ore veins, the survey must be detailed (10–20 meter step).

2. Field Separation (Transformations). The main problem in gravity exploration is signal overlap, i.e., as a result of the measurement, a complex observed field is obtained, on which local and regional anomalies are superimposed. Deep, dense masses create a regional component, while shallow masses and orebodies create sharp peaks in the local component. The "Averaging" method helps remove fine details and reveal deep structures, and by subtracting this anomaly from the observed field, the local component of the original field is obtained. Calculations using the derivative method emphasize the boundaries of objects and "highlight" shallow deposits [5, 6].

3. Solving the inverse problem involves attempting to determine the parameters of an object based on its field, selecting its shape (layer, sphere, cylinder), calculating the excess mass of the orebody, allowing for an approximate estimate of the deposit's reserves before drilling, and determining the position of the upper edge of the deposit. It should be noted that the inverse problem is not uniquely solved, and therefore direct modeling plays an important role in reducing ambiguity [1, 4]. In this case, a geophysicist constructs a hypothetical model of the section based on geological concepts. A computer calculates the signal such a model should produce. If the calculated graph matches the measured one, the model is considered plausible.

Below are presented the mathematical foundations of numerical modeling for simple and complex homogeneous ore deposit models to assess their gravitational

influence. To achieve maximum realism, inclined ellipsoids were used to model a continuous ore body with smooth boundaries. The centers of mass of these ellipsoids were located at different depths typical of ore bodies, using the following formulas:

$$V_z = G \Delta \sigma \iint_s \frac{z}{((x-\xi)^2 + z^2)^{1.5}} \quad (1)$$

$$V_{xz} = \frac{\partial V_z}{\partial x}; \quad V_{zz} = \frac{\partial V_z}{\partial z}, \quad (2)$$

where s is the domain bounded by the equation of a two-dimensional oblique ellipse.

Calculations and visualization of the theoretical curves were performed using Python code generated by the Gemini AI model [11].

Result and discussion

To approximate the model to reality, an elongated two-dimensional ellipse was chosen as the ore body model. During the numerical modeling, a comparative analysis of the gravitational influence of a massive ore body (600 m long, 80 m thick) located at a depth of 300 m was performed at various angles of occurrence: 0° (horizontal), 45° (inclined), and 90° (vertical). For the calculations, an excess density of 0.8 g/cm³ was chosen for the ore body, which is typical for massive sulfides among granites. The calculation (observation) profile covers a distance from -1000 to +1000 meters. When horizontal, the anomaly is characterized by a wide, flat-topped dome with an amplitude of approximately 1.1 mGal (Fig. 1). This is a reliably recorded value for modern ground-

Fig. 1. Theoretical model of the gravity field and its derivatives for a horizontal ore body in the shape of an elongated ellipse

based gravity surveys, with an accuracy of up to 0.001 mGal. The anomaly's width is at half the amplitude and is directly related to the body's depth. The horizontal gravity gradient is symmetrical and reaches its extremes precisely above the body's edges, allowing its horizontal boundaries to be determined with high accuracy. The maximum amplitude of the horizontal gradient is ± 1.8 E. The maximum and minimum gradients are equal in magnitude and are located precisely above the formation's edges (marks of -18 and $+18$ E). The amplitude of positive vertical gradient values is 8 E,

while the amplitude of negative values limits the horizontal edges of the ore body and is -4 E.

If the ore body is vertical, the maximum anomaly intensity (up to 2.2 mGal) is recorded due to the concentration of mass along the vertical axis (Fig. 2). The anomaly becomes compact, and the vertical gradient forms a sharp peak, ideally localizing the ore shoot axis. The horizontal gradient is the best method for finding vertical faults. Above the vertical contact of two rock blocks, it will produce a single sharp peak, marking a zone of tectonic disturbance.

In the case of an inclined position of the ore body at an angle of approximately 45° , a sharp violation of the symmetry of the fields is observed (Fig. 3). The maximum value of the vertical gradient is shifted toward the uplifted edge of the body, approximately 250 m from the center of mass. Due to the tilt of the ore body, the right branch of the gravity anomaly curve is less steep than the left branch and is also shifted to the right (the maximum of the blue line is located to the right of zero at approximately 125 m). This allows the geophysicist to determine the direction of the deposit's dip and proves that drilling at the anomaly's maximum will only intersect the upper edge of the deposit, ignoring its bulk. The asymmetry of the peaks serves as a reliable indicator of the formation's dip direction and confirms that in gravity surveys, the "apparent" center of the

anomaly is always shifted toward the upper edge of the inclined body. The horizontal gradient shows a strong negative peak, while the vertical gradient shows a strong positive peak on the right—a response to the ore approaching the surface.

Comparison of orebody models with different orientations shows that the anomaly amplitude depends not only on the mass of the object but also on its spatial orientation. Increasing the tilt angle relative to the horizontal position leads to an increase in signal intensity while simultaneously narrowing the anomalous zone (Fig. 4). The gravity intensity changes from 4.5 mGal to approximately 2.7 mGal. The use of gradients is crucial for resolving interpretation ambiguities, as they allow one to distinguish a deep-seated massive body from a series of small, near-surface objects.

Fig. 2. Theoretical model of the gravity field and its derivatives for a vertically located ore body

Fig. 3. Theoretical model of the gravity field and its derivatives for an inclined ore body

Fig. 4. Comparative analysis of the gravity response for a massive elongated body ($L = 1200$ m) at different dip angles

The orebody model was then further complicated and represented by two inclined lenses located at equal depths (600 m) and gradually approaching each other in the horizontal direction (Fig. 5). In the case where the inclined orebodies are located 2,400 m apart, all three curves represent these two orebodies separately, just as in the case of a single inclined orebody (Fig. 5a). When these bodies are spaced 800 m apart (Fig. 5b), i.e., close to each other, the shape of the curves changes. The gravity curve (blue curve) becomes flat with a slight disruption of symmetry (reflecting a single ore body). The vertical gradient is represented by two closely spaced maxima, clearly indicating the presence of two bodies. The horizontal gradient curve (green curve) is represented by one positive maximum and one negative minimum gradient with a slight increase in complexity between them, indicating the presence of two bodies.

In the following graph (Fig. 6), these two bodies are brought into close proximity (200 m between the centers of gravity), and all curves display a single maximum of gravity, horizontal, and vertical gradients. As can be seen, if the bodies are brought to a size one-third

the size of the ore body itself for a given burial depth, their influence is not visually reflected in the corresponding gravity curves and their gradients.

The ore body model was then further refined, representing two inclined lenses (ore bodies) located at different depths (300 and 500 m) and at different horizontal distances from each other (Fig. 7). When the distance between them is 1,400 m, the positive and negative extrema of the curves for these bodies have different amplitudes (Fig. 7a). This is a key feature for distinguishing inclined ore bodies located at different depths. When the horizontal distance between them is 400 m, the gravity curve for a 600 x 80 m ore body exhibits a single maximum with an intensity of 1.4 mGal (Fig. 7b). The left branch above the nearby portion of the ore body is steeper than the right branch. A low-intensity positive maximum appears on the right branch of the vertical gradient curve, indicating the presence of a second, deeper-lying ore body. A similar picture is observed on the horizontal gradient curve, on the right negative branch of which a low-intensity maximum of the horizontal gradient appears.

Conclusions:

1. The exploration of ore deposits using gravity data was analyzed. Ore deposits have excess density and are therefore well represented in the gravity field. The stages of processing and interpreting gravity data

were defined to identify local anomalies associated with ore deposits. Solving the direct problem and modeling gravity anomalies play an important role in the interpretation process when exploring for ore deposits.

a (distance 2400 m); *b* (distance 800 m)

Fig. 5. Theoretical model of the gravity field and its derivatives for two parallel ore bodies at different distances

Fig. 6. Theoretical model of the gravitational field and its derivatives for two parallel ore bodies (distance 200 m)

a (distance 1400 m); *b* (distance 400 m)

Fig. 7. Theoretical model of the gravity field and its derivatives for two ore bodies located at different depths

2. A two-dimensional model of the ore deposit was created in the form of an elongated ellipse, occurring at various depths and with different orientations. The physical and geometric parameters of the ore deposit model were determined. Gravity curves, as well as horizontal and vertical gravity gradients, were calculated and plotted. These curves were interpreted, analyzed, and demonstrated the possibility of identifying local anomalies associated with isolated ore deposits.

3. A more complex two-dimensional model of the ore deposit was constructed, consisting of two parallel, elongated ellipses inclined at approximately 45° , lying at equal and different depths and at varying horizontal distances from each other. A comprehensive analysis of the gravity curve shape, as well as the vertical and horizontal gradients, allowed us not only to confirm the presence of excess masses but also to accurately delineate the ore deposit, defining its horizontal boundaries.

References

1. İsgandarov E.H. Digital modeling of the gravity field of the Muradkhanli uplift. Australian Journal of Education and Science. Australia. Sidney universiteti. 2018 il, 9.p.
2. İsgandarov E., H., Dadashly G. Possibilities of underground gravity exploration, Earth Sciences, German International Journal of Modern Science, №47, 2022, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7495578>
3. İsgandarov E., Fetullayeva A. Possibilities of underground magnetic exploration. Sciences of Europe, Praha, Czech Republic. No 109 (2023), pp.44-48., ISSN 3162-2364. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7560373>
4. İsgandarov E.H. Digital estimation of the gravitational effect of the crystalline basement of the Yevlakh-Agjabadi Basin (Middle-Kur Depression), Azerbaijan National Akademy of sciences. ANAS Transactions Earth Sciences, Geology and Geophysics institute. ISSN 2218-8754, 2023, № 1.(Scobus), pp. 17-24.
5. İsgandarov E.H., İsgandarova L.E. Application of computer technology to solve the problem of gravimetry. Journal of science, Lyon, France, № 48/2023, pp. 6-11, ISSN 3475-3281, <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10277016>.
<https://www.doi.org/10.33677/ggianas20230100090>
6. İsgandarov E.H., Kirgizbayev A., İsgandarova L.E. Transformation of gravi -magnetic anomalies on the computer. Italy's scientific journal Annali d'Italia,

№53, 2024, pp.12-19, pdf, ISSN 3572-2436.,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10869374>

7. Mironov V. S. Gravity exploration. - L.: Nedra, 1980, 543 p. (In Russian)

8. Richard J. Blakely. Potential Theory in Gravity and Magnetic Applications. Cambridge University Press, 2009, p.461.

9. Serkerov S. A. Gravity and magnetic exploration. - M.: Nedra, 2006, p.479. (In Russian)

10. Znamensky V. V. Field geophysics. - M.: Nedra, 1980. 351 p. (In Russian)

11. Google. (2026). Gemini (April 25 version) [Large language model]. google.com